

CHALLAENGES FACED BY HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS IN LEARNING CHEMISTRY AS A DISCIPLINE

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Abstract

Science is considered as an important subject in school curriculum as the man's future depends to a large extent on scientific advances and development of productive activity. Science has led us to find out things that give us what we have today. A world without Science would mean that we would still be living in a very difficult way to that of what we live today. Teaching the scientific methods to students is teaching them how to think, learn, solve problems and make decisions. These skills are integral to every aspects of students education and life from school to career.

However it is mostly observed that these skills lack in the students. If the students would not be able to reflect what they study in the classrooms, it is of no use.

The objectives of this study was to examine the nature and causes of common difficulties experienced by Higher Secondary students in learning Chemistry as a discipline and ways to minimize these difficulties in learning Chemistry.

Students face many problems in topics like Chemical Bonding, Thermodynamics, Chemical Equilibrium and Colligative properties.

The main factors that are contributed for learning difficulties include-

Absence of lab work, absence of teaching and learning resource, poor teaching and learning strategies, poor English and Mathematical skills and so there is a need to improve these causes.

Teachers also focus on only those aspects which gain examination grades rather than favourable outcomes like developing practical skills and attitudes.

Keywords : scientific method, learning strategies, attitude, practical skills, learning resources, productivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The curriculum of Chemistry incorporates many abstract topics and principles. The major problem is the abstract nature of many topics which students fail to grasp as it is different from everyday life experience.

The difficulty is further raised by lack of experimental activities in labs, non-availability of reference books and not appropriate explanation by teachers.

Topics like Thermodynamics, Chemical Equilibrium, Chemical Kinetics which are very important topics for all sorts of examination but students fail to understand the basic concepts of it due to various factors and especially the incapability of teachers to teach the topic in the manner it should have been taught.

Teachers should create the learning environment in which learners should be engaged in active learning by engaging learners in constructing higher order thinking mental capacities like concepts, procedures predicting and justifying with each other. A healthy competition should be encouraged among students by providing opportunities for students demonstration, organizing field trips, Science clubs and fairs and here the role of the teacher is only to facilitate the learning of the students.

There is a huge gap seen between what is intended in curriculum in terms of students' learning in Chemistry and what actually happens in classroom. Also there is a wide difference in the curriculum of Secondary and Higher Secondary curriculum. These gaps must be filled for a better result.

A research was conducted at the Ebinat Preparatory school in Ethopia of Grade 12 Students studying Chemistry and the

Results in the past four consecutive years are given in the following table.

Ebinat Preparatory School 12 Students Model Examination Results from 2012 to 2015.

Year	Registered Candidates Total	Passed Candidates in Exam		Failed Candidates in Exam	
		Total	%	Total	%
2012	136	57	41.90	79	58.10
2013	247	92	37.24	155	62.76
2014	266	104	39.10	162	60.90
2015	284	107	37.67	177	62.32
Total	933	360	38.98	573	61.02

As can be seen from table that the pass percentage of students in the four years went 38.98%. It is clear from the table that a large percentage of candidates in the four years given just failed in school examinations. Again in 2012, 79(58.10%) out of 136, in 2013, 155 (62.76%) out of 247, in 2014, 162(60.90%) out of 247 and finally in 2015, 177 (62.32%) out of 284 students are failed from total registered candidates respectively.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study was to examine the nature and causes of common difficulties experienced by Higher secondary students in learning Chemistry as a discipline and ways to minimize these difficulties in learning Chemistry.

III. MAJOR AREAS AND CONCEPTS : CHALLENGES FACED BY STUDENTS

The following are the lists of some topics of Senior Secondary Grade in which students face challenges:

i. Chemical Equilibrium

Most students find Chemical Equilibrium difficult as they consider reaction quotient and equilibrium constant are same

as the way we calculate reaction quotient is very similar to equilibrium constant. Due to these misconceptions, in equilibrium, students fail to calculate equilibrium constant and memorize the formula. Students also find problem in solving the numerical problems.

Example : Let us consider a reaction-

In order to know whether the reaction would be favoured in forward or in backward direction, we need to see the value of K_c (Equilibrium Constant).

If $K_c > 10^3$ then reaction will move in forward direction otherwise in backward direction.

Reaction Quotient is denoted as Q_c and it is written as, $(\text{HBr})^2 / (\text{H}_2)(\text{Br}_2)$ for the above reaction.

Now if $Q = K_c$, Reaction will be in equilibrium.

$Q > K_c$, Q tend to decrease so as to become equal to K_c .

- Reaction will be in backward direction.

$Q < K_c$, Q tend to increase so as to become equal to K_c .

- Reaction will be in forward direction.

This is the most basic concept but students often get confused in calculating them.

ii. Chemical Kinetics

Students find this topic very complex. They consider rate constant as same in all orders of reaction. So they fail to calculate rate constant and rate of forward and backward reaction. They also find reaction mechanism difficult as they fail to understand the nature of reaction.

One of the most basic concept of this topic in which students find difficulty is to calculate the Molecularity and Order of reaction.

Example : Consider a reaction – $2\text{NO}(\text{g}) + \text{O}_2(\text{g}) \rightleftharpoons 2\text{NO}_2(\text{g})$

As we know that Molecularity is the no. of reacting species (molecules, atoms or ions) which are taking part in an elementary reaction.

This reaction is Trimolecular as 3 molecules of reactants are taking part in an elementary reaction.

Order of a reaction is the sum of powers of the concentration of reactants in the rate law expression.

In order to calculate the Order of reaction we first need to calculate the rate of reaction.

Here, **Rate** = $K(\text{NO})^2(\text{O}_2)$. So **overall Order** = 3

iii. **Chemical Bonding**

Students find most of the terms abstract in Chemical Bonding and they just mug it up. They have poor concept of hybridization like they are not able to distinguish between Sp^1 , Sp^2 , Sp^3 hybridization and the concept of valence electrons and how atoms share electrons.

Also they are not able to distinguish between the various types of bonds which are already introduced in secondary classes and so they are not able to draw the electron dot structure of various atoms and compounds.

Example: Teachers must connect the topics to their daily life experiences in order to make the learning concrete and permanent.

i. **Ionic Bonding**

In order to explain the ionic bonding in compound NaCl they can introduce it like this – Group 1 and Group 2 elements are rich person and Group 17 elements are poor. Now as we all know that all elements tend to achieve noble gas configuration.

Electronic configuration of Na – 2, 8, 1. Since it has 1 valence electron it can easily lose it in order to achieve noble gas

configuration of Neon which is (2, 8).

Chlorine belongs to group 17 and they are poor elements.

Electronic Configuration of Cl -2, 8, 7. In order to achieve next noble gas configuration of Argon it requires one electron. So it will take electron from sodium as it is rich in electrons.

So there exists ionic bond in compound NaCl.

Electron dot structure is shown as :

ii. Covalent Bonding

Similarly, in order to explain covalent bonding between Nitrogen atoms,

It can be introduced like this –

Suppose 2 friends went to a hotel for lunch but they did not have enough money for it. So they thought to share the lunch as well as bill among themselves. So in this case both of them earned the profit of having lunch at less price. Same is the case with covalent bonding.

The elements share the electrons among themselves in order to achieve noble gas configuration.

Electron dot structure of Nitrogen is as follows:

Here both the nitrogen atoms has 5 valence electrons so they shared 3 electrons among themselves in order to attain noble gas configuration.

iii. Metallic Bonding

This type of bond is found in metals in this electron clouds are formed around the metal atoms. This is the reason for good electrical conductivity in metals.

Example:

So in this manner these topics should be connected to daily life experiences and taught in the classroom.

iv. Thermodynamics

This is a very important and interesting chapter if it is learned in right manner. But here also students fail to understand the concept clearly. Students find difficulty in terms like work, heat, specific heat, specific heat capacity, system and surrounding confusing and they have difficulty in differentiating terms like heat with work, specific heat with specific heat capacity and on the system with by the system.

v. Colligative Properties

Students find difficult to remember and differentiate the formula of Colligative Properties with concentration parameters like mole fraction, molality, molarity.

They don't have clear idea of basic concepts like Vapour pressure lowering, Boiling point elevation, Freezing point depression and Osmotic pressure.

IV. Causes of Learning Difficulties

i. Absence of Lab Work

Chemistry topics need experiments to understand in order to

have clear view of the topic. But due to absence of lab class, apparatus and chemicals in school, this is usually not done.

Example : Salt analysis, Titration for detection of acid and basic radicals need detailed explanation and practice as it is the most important concept of Chemistry for all grades.

ii. Inadequate Explanation from Teachers

This subject requires trained teachers who have command over the subject. Teachers fail to explain the laws, facts and rules due to lack of skills and knowledge in the subject.

iii. Wide Syllabus

Teachers fail to cover the entire syllabus as the topics and the period allotted to them do not match.

Example: Topics like Chemical bonding, Thermodynamics, Biomolecules, P and D block elements need more time for detailed explanation.

iv. Lack of Mathematical Skills

Students face problem in calculating the numerical problems as the teachers do not provide the necessary techniques to tackle it.

Example : Topics like Solution, Electrochemistry, Chemical Kinetics are full of numericals in which students often get confused.

v. Lack of Remedial Action by Teachers

Teachers do not provide any remedial action to slow learners. They take into account only the fast learners leaving slow learners aside. As a result, students fail to fill the the gaps and they fail in examination.

vi. Lack of Motivation and Language Skills

Most students lack internal motivation and they fail to understand English. As a result, they do not participate in class discussion so they perform poor in examination also.

vii. Lack of Teaching and Learning Aid

Lack of supplementary books and learning resources affect the performance of students. Updated and authentic books are not available in library and also the ratio of students and textbook is not appropriate.

As a result, students develop negative attitude towards Chemistry.

V. Measures to be applied to minimize learning difficulties in Chemistry as a discipline

The different measures are as follows :

i. Teaching and Learning Aids

Chemistry is a wide subject, so appropriate books should be made available in library to cover the topics which teachers fail to cover during class hours. Learning facilities should be improved by proper use of smart class and laboratory.

ii. Teaching of Challenging Topic

Teachers should teach the difficult topics in the simplest manner possible so that any level of student can understand it. Topics should be revised at regular intervals and motivation should be provided to students.

Example: Topics like D and F block elements, Coordination compounds, Electrochemistry need explanation from the ground level.

iii. Provision of Experimental Work

In most of the schools, lab work is only done few days before examination and so the students do not overlap necessary skills to carry out experiments. Chemical should be available in proper amounts in order to enable each student to carry out work.

Example: Salt analysis and titration is the heart of Chemistry practical but students don't know the necessary process to carry out the experiments.

iv. Improvement in Assessment

Regular test must be taken after covering each topic by the teachers and practical questions should also be included in the test.

Teachers must check the assignments of learners regularly and contact to the parents of children in order to increase the motivation in learners.

v. Use of Proper English Language by Teachers

Teachers should use simple English words in class so that each student can understand. It is also just not the duty of just English teacher to teach English in class, other teachers also carry equal responsibility as different subjects have different meanings of same word.

Language should be clear and valid to the context.

vi. Avoid Hiding Information

Teachers should not be in a rush and avoid hiding necessary information of any topic. Teachers should create positive environment in class by taking into account all types of learners. The teaching strategies should match with the level of students.

More time should be given to difficult topics and teaching aids should be used in dealing with abstract concepts like Chemical Bonding, Electrochemistry, organic Compounds like Haloarenes, Haloalkanes, Process of isolation of elements.

vii. Provision of Qualified Teachers

There shall be provision of competent teachers. Ratio of

students and teacher should be balanced and proper interaction should be developed between them. Number of periods allocated each week should also be increased to cover the syllabus on time.

CONCLUSION

Chemistry is not an easy discipline to study. It is often regarded as a difficult subject and so most of the learners repel themselves from learning it. In schools and colleges, the lecture is probably the oldest and appropriate teaching method is not adopted to make the subject effective and enriching. In this traditional method, the students' engagement in the process of learning is quite low and so students assume a passive, non- thinking, information receiving role. So the common assumption that lecture is an efficient way to transfer knowledge accurately, is wrong. Students are not able to understand the key and technical terms and hence could not develop reflective learning which leads to rote memorization. Some of the topics demand extra concern and preparation from the part of teachers.

This article reveals that some topics in Chemistry like Chemical Equilibrium, Chemical Bonding, Kinetics, Thermodynamics and Colligative Properties are difficult. Most of the time teachers are also unable to explain the subject matter as they face shortage of time to complete the syllabus. There are also causes like absence of teaching and learning resources, labs and poor methods of teaching. So there is a need to support theoretical learners with practical activities. In order to explain the topics teachers should connect the topics to real life experiences of learners. This makes their learning permanent and concrete. Visual aids should also be used so that students having different learning styles can easily grasp the topic. In this manner students learning could be enhanced in a better level.

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